

Explainable AI through the lens of Legitimate AI

JASPER VAN DER WAA and MARISSA HOEKSTRA, TNO, Netherlands

Fig. 1. Explanations through the lens of legitimacy and its four aspects relating to steps in an AI's life-cycle. These aspects reveal questions that a person subjected to automated decisions may have to judge the legitimacy of that automation. Questions that a more explainable AI system can help answer.

Explainable AI (XAI) is frequently linked to responsible AI, under the assumption that it allows organisations to implement AI responsibly. However, with AI's growing use in civic settings, the number of people subjected to (partially) automated decisions rises, which should make us question if explanations from a responsible AI perspective would also benefit these subjects. We propose legitimate AI as an alternative and more relevant perspective to guide explainable AI (XAI) research focused on these subjects. If subjects are aided in their judgement of whether an AI is legitimate, they can serve as a societal check if the development and usage of an AI were done responsibly. In addition, explanations supporting that judgment enable them to decide to contest or accept a decision. We outline four aspects of legitimacy and their relevance to XAI, discussing a subject's potential questions for each aspect, highlighting topics that are currently under-explored. This perspective also uncovers the complexity of explanations aimed at empowering subjects, as such explanations need to reveal complex and intertwined topics through limited to no direct interaction.

CCS Concepts: • **Human-centered computing** → **Human computer interaction (HCI)**; • **Social and professional topics** → *Computing / technology policy*; • **Computing methodologies** → **Artificial intelligence**; • **Security and privacy** → Human and societal aspects of security and privacy.

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1 Introduction

The topic of explainable AI (XAI) is often related to the need to have AI that is implemented and used responsibly [1, 12, 38]. Responsibility in AI considers the extent to which developers, data agencies, auditing organisations, and similar executive organisations ensure that an AI meets ethical expectations and behaves within legal boundaries [1, 6, 36]. From this perspective, XAI is a means of obtaining the necessary insights to determine if an AI is ethical and legal [2]. In addition, XAI has been discussed as a means for users to obtain insights for purposes such as collaboration [33],

Authors' Contact Information: Jasper van der Waa, jasper.vanderwaa@tno.nl; Marissa Hoekstra, marissa.hoekstra@tno.nl, TNO, Soesterberg, Utrecht, Netherlands.

Fig. 2. Two perspectives to Explainable AI. Responsible AI focuses on executive organisations whereas Legitimate AI focuses on those subjected to the use of an AI. Whether an AI is deemed legitimate or not, should dictate if executive organisations took their societal and legal responsibility.

trust [15], and acceptance [24]. In short, the perspective of responsible AI is applied by executive organisations, such as developers, data agencies, and auditing organisations – those held responsible for an AI. The perspective of legitimate AI applies to those subjected to an AI, such as patients, loan applicants, and those suspected of fraud – those judging the use of an AI. See 2 for this distinction. In this work, we focus on the subject and argue that the perspective of legitimacy is better suited to identify their needs than the responsible AI perspective.

This work contributes to the HCXAI'25 workshop topic of promoting responsible AI practices by arguing for a change in perspective when dealing with the subject role. Legitimacy is a term for public policy, and this work illustrates how XAI can draw inspiration from that field. As subjects are most prevalent in civic applications of AI (i.e., the public domain [34]), this work is also relevant for the workshop's civic AI theme.

Legitimacy in the context of AI is about its behaviour and sociotechnical system “being desirable, proper or appropriate within some socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs, and definitions” [35]. Legitimacy is relational, with a behaving entity and a judging entity involved [19]. For legitimate AI, those who are subjected to an AI judge its legitimacy, not the executive organisations who are responsible for ensuring that it is legitimate. These subjects have their data collected, processed and used in the advancement and development of AI [9, 16]. They experience the effects of AI decisions as it is deployed. Subjects are not the users of an AI. A user receives support from that AI for their decision-making or employs it to achieve particular goals [9]. A user is in a position to ensure the responsible use of an AI. Instead, a subject is the person who judges whether the use of an AI aligns with their norms and values. As such, when dealing with the information needs of a subject, the perspective of legitimacy is better suited than the perspective of responsibility.

XAI's role concerning legitimacy is to provide individuals with the necessary understanding to judge whether an AI and its sociotechnical system align to their norms and values. In the literature, this is mainly limited to empowering subjects to contest AI outcomes [25]. Our work introduces the perspective of legitimacy and illustrates that this can reveal new questions and needs that are currently being overlooked.

2 Aspects of legitimacy

This work follows the definition from Suchman [35] which defines legitimacy as a relational concept based on the judgment of behaviour in terms of norms, values, beliefs and definitions. This recognises that what is legitimate is fluid by nature as the basis of judgement changes with cultures and experience [3, 19, 20]. Often, legitimacy is portrayed as

multidimensional; with an ethical dimension (is this AI ethical?), a legal dimension (is this AI allowed?), a political dimension (does this AI reflect my community?) and a societal dimension (should I accept this AI?) [5].

In the context of AI, and particular XAI, a system approach to legitimacy seems most relevant. First introduced by Scharpf [30], a system approach underlines the need for a holistic view towards legitimacy and that it consists of different intertwined aspects. These aspects are input and output legitimacy [30], throughput legitimacy [17, 31], and outcome legitimacy [5, pp. 60-61]. When mapped to AI, these relate to questions such as “Was my community represented in the development of this AI?” (input), “How is this AI involved in decision-making?” (throughput), “Is this AI reliable?” (output), and “Am I treated the same as others?” (outcome). This system approach to legitimacy matches the call from the HCXAI community for a more holistic and sociotechnical view toward XAI [13, 28, 32].

Below we describe each aspect in more detail in relation to XAI and discuss the new research directions the perspective of legitimacy reveals. Figure 1 illustrates the four aspects and the subject’s judgment call for each with examples of questions the subject may have. This figure also illustrates that a subject’s judgement allows them to decide to contest or accept an AI’s decision. If the subject decides to contest the decision, this could lead to the acceptance or rejection of their concerns by an executive organisation. When accepted, this may result in an improved version of the AI, a decision to use it differently, or to discard its use entirely. When a subject’s concerns are rejected, a conflict arises between the subject as society’s representative and an executive organisation responsible for the AI. A conflict that could be resolved through mediation or legal steps. The perspective of legitimacy on XAI, reveals that subjects should be empowered to make the necessary judgement calls. The four aspects of legitimacy allow for the identification of distinct questions to be answered.

2.1 Input legitimacy

Input legitimacy is about understanding what went into the development of an AI and judging that development process. It is important for the subject to understand if they were sufficiently represented during development and how this shaped the eventual AI and its surrounding sociotechnical system. For example, a subject’s judgment on the legitimacy of an AI is affected when they realise that this AI was not tested on bias that could be harmful to them. Similarly, a subject’s data may have been used in the development or testing of the AI, and they might wonder if and how they consented to this. For XAI to support subjects in their judgment regarding input legitimacy, these questions need to be identified and answered before subjects can judge whether their norms and values were sufficiently represented.

These topics often relate to legal transparency requirements [18] that state that such information should be present in the event of legal disputes. Here, we argue that for subjects to judge if an AI is legitimate, they require this information to be explained to them when confronted with the use of an AI. HCXAI strongly advocates for the recognition and participation of subjects in the research, design, and development of XAI [13]. Input legitimacy offers a lens through which that involvement and impact can be disclosed to subjects.

2.2 Throughput legitimacy

Throughput legitimacy is about a subject’s judgement on how an AI is used in the decision-making process, including its oversight. For subjects, it is important to understand that an AI is used in the first place. Not all use of AI is always obvious. Second, they should know what role an AI played and the broader sociotechnical system in which it operates. For example, if an AI only collected and presented data to a decision-maker who is regularly audited or made a decision entirely on its own with minimal human oversight. Finally, a subject should understand what parties are involved in assessing if they trust those parties in their role. For example, an AI assisting a physician to achieve better diagnoses

might be experienced differently than an AI assisting a medical student to allow them to act as a physician to help reduce their workload. Although the AI might be the same, the way it is used can be a reason for a subject to judge it illegitimate.

The aspect of throughput legitimacy seems to be a more prevalent topic in XAI compared to input legitimacy. For example, see the research on procedural fairness and the role of explanations address how subjects may contest the way an AI is used [29, 32, 39]. Similarly, the work of Yurrita et al. [40] introduces process-centred explanations that explain the decision-making process of an AI with the aim of empowering subjects to scrutinise this process. Throughput legitimacy implies more than these explanations on the AI's functioning. Explanations may also address the degree of human involvement, the organisations involved in the decision-making process, or who can view a subject's data. Throughput legitimacy underlines the need to expand towards a more social and holistic take on XAI, where explanations address more than an AI's functioning [10, 11].

2.3 Output legitimacy

Output legitimacy is about understanding and judging the benefits and risks the AI's contribution to a decision offers a subject. If an AI makes a decision that affects the subject, they should be able to understand if this is in their best interest. Subjects, for example, may want to know if the use of that AI results in a better or more efficient decision for them. Alternatively, they may want to know if cases like theirs result in correct and consistent outputs. Output legitimacy in relation to XAI is about allowing subjects to judge if an AI's output offers any value to them without introducing undue risk.

It seems that so far a limited number of explanations have been identified to help subjects judge if an AI's output is beneficial to them. Research on explanations that help AI users assess the disparity in error rates between demographic groups may come closest [7, 32]. Such explanations might also prove to be useful in communicating to subjects the differences in an AI's performance between their demographic group and others. However, these explanations must be adapted to a subject instead of a user role. Technical work on explanations that convey the consistency [27] and confidence of an AI [37] might offer similar directions, but require similar adaptations.

2.4 Outcome legitimacy

Outcome legitimacy concerns the judgement if the effects of a decision with an AI's involvement are acceptable to the subject. It refers to the fairness, relevance, and accuracy of a decision and its consequences. Subjects may wonder how the decision was made, what data was used, and what the importance of certain data was. Here, subjects may also ask themselves if they are able to understand how the AI functions and if that understanding is sufficient for them to feel confident in their judgment of its legitimacy.

Outcome legitimacy is at present the most researched, as it relates to explaining the (un)fairness of a decision and allows subjects to contest it if necessary. This is not without its challenges, as such explanations might leave the subject believing that an AI is fair when it is not [32]. Although the principle of fair treatment might be the most prevalent topic in the literature regarding outcome legitimacy, it is not the only one. Another relevant topic of explanation are the consequences of a decision in the first place [21]. Not all subjects in every domain might be able to understand this easily (e.g., patients with low health literacy who have trouble understanding an AI-aided diagnosis). The ability to recognise the consequences of a decision forms the basis for the subject's agency to determine whether and how to judge the legitimacy of decisions [22, 23]. Finally, common ethical principles such as accountability (i.e., who is

responsible for the consequences?) and privacy (i.e., who knows about this decision and its consequences?) could prove to be equally important depending on the domain, decision, and subject.

3 Example: welfare benefits fraud scoring

To further clarify the value of the legitimacy perspective for XAI, we map it to a real-world case. Rotterdam, a major Dutch city, used an AI to score the risk of fraud among citizens on their welfare benefits from 2017 to 2021 [8, 14]. These citizens were the subjects of this AI. The executive organisations comprised of the Rotterdam municipality using this AI and its developer Accenture. They were tasked with ensuring that the AI was developed and used responsibly. This AI, a gradient boosting model, used 315 attributes to provide a score to around 30.000 citizens, using around 500 decision trees. The attributes used ranged from the gender, age and financial status of the subject to more invasive attributes, such as the duration of their last romantic relationship. In addition, attributes included if any comment fields were filled in by case workers, such as on the subject's ability to handle pressure, their motivation, attitude, appearance, and ability to be flexible. Of the 30.000 citizens analysed, roughly 10% received a sufficiently high risk score that warranted a deeper investigation.

The Responsible AI perspective towards XAI would dictate that the executive organisations should understand this AI sufficiently to decide how it can be used in an acceptable and legal manner. The Legitimate AI perspective towards XAI instead highlights the importance for the citizens, as subjects of the AI, to understand that an AI was used (throughput legitimacy), what data it used (input legitimacy), what their risk score was and why (output legitimacy), and how this resulted in an invasive investigation of their private life (outcome legitimacy). A WIRED article illustrates where explanations are used to disclose information for subjects [8]. It uses feature attributions to reveal the influence of questionable features on the outputted risk score (input legitimacy). In addition, it communicates several counterfactual explanations based on illustrative personas of typical subjects through 'scrollytelling' (output legitimacy). Research on XAI should not focus solely on helping executive organisations in their efforts to implement AI responsibly. Research should also address how subjects and those that act on their interests, such as journalists and NGO's, can be empowered to make a judgement call if an AI is indeed developed and used responsibly.

4 Empowering explanations

A subject's judgment if an AI and its use is legitimate is a means for society as a whole to be able to accept or disregard particular uses of AI. However, it is not the only added value of this judgment. It also serves the individual subject in their decision to contest or accept the decision with an AI's involvement. This requires the explanations not only to inform subjects but also to empower them to make a judgement and take appropriate action. This requires the suggestion of concrete actions that a subject can take [26]. For example, an explanation should not only convey the potential bias in a decision (outcome legitimacy), but also offer a suggestion who to contact to correct or mitigate this.

The four legitimacy aspects are intertwined and complementary to each other. First, it is not as if one legitimacy aspect is violated, the use of that AI suddenly becomes entirely illegitimate. This final judgment involves a personal weighing of a subject's own norms and values. Explanations should support this weighing by addressing multiple, if not all, aspects at a time to reveal important relations between them. For example, an explanation can address all aspects at once by explaining that a particular decision is biased (outcome legitimacy), but that this is inconsistent with other past decisions (output legitimacy) and occurred despite the involvement of the subject's demographic group in the AI's design (input legitimacy) with no option to address this to at present (throughput legitimacy). Such an explanation addressing all aspects offers the subject the necessary overview to decide if they want to take action and what that

action might be. Combined with clear suggestions on how they can act (e.g., report to an oversight committee), this would empower them greatly.

An open question remains how such explanations should be communicated to subjects. By definition, they are not in direct interaction with an AI. At best, they are informed by the AI or a human decision maker (e.g., during a doctor visit), at worse, they are informed through a static message (e.g., a letter from a government agency). Since the necessary explanations are likely multi-faceted and information dense, it is better to communicate them in an interactive manner such as through an explanatory dialogue [41] or an exploratory interface [4]. Alternatively, subjects may engage in conversation with someone who can explain this to them, who in turn has access to such dialogue and exploratory interfaces. Either option requires significant effort from organisations to implement. It would require a more involved interaction with the decision makers or an additional point of interaction with an AI.

The legitimacy perspective offers the HCXAI community a way to frame the needs of the subjects to empower them. At the same time, it reveals the complexity of supporting and empowering subjects in the reality of civil applications of AI.

5 Implications

Subjects, as individuals affected by AI decisions, should have the ability to challenge an AI's usage by judging its legitimacy based on their norms and values. This is the perspective of legitimacy for XAI in which subjects are empowered through explanations to signal illegitimate use of AI due to, for example, irresponsible development practices. We discussed four legitimacy aspects: input, throughput, output, and outcome, connecting them to potential questions a subject may have to inspire future topics for explanations. These include typical topics from XAI literature such as counterfactuals and procedural fairness, as well as novel ones like the degree of design participation and the benefits of an AI's usage for subjects. Legitimacy and its four aspects offer an interesting new perspective on an existing challenge. In addition, it serves as a frame that reveals the complexity of such explanations with topics being intertwined and the difficulty of communicating them. Subjects will rarely be in a position to interact directly with the explanations. How will we communicate complex and intertwined topics to them in a way that empowers them to make the necessary judgements and take appropriate action? This is a question that needs to be answered as we, as the HCXAI community, continue to pose explanations as a means of subject empowerment.

References

- [1] Alejandro Barredo Arrieta, Natalia Díaz-Rodríguez, Javier Del Ser, Adrien Bennetot, Siham Tabik, Alberto Barbado, Salvador García, Sergio Gil-López, Daniel Molina, Richard Benjamins, et al. 2020. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI): Concepts, taxonomies, opportunities and challenges toward responsible AI. *Information fusion* 58 (2020), 82–115.
- [2] Richard Benjamins, Alberto Barbado, and Daniel Sierra. 2019. Responsible AI by design in practice. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1909.12838* (2019).
- [3] Steven Bernstein. 2004. Legitimacy in global environmental governance. *J. Int'l L & Int'l Rel.* 1 (2004), 139.
- [4] Maalvika Bhat and Duri Long. 2024. Designing Interactive Explainable AI Tools for Algorithmic Literacy and Transparency. In *Proceedings of the 2024 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference*. 939–957.
- [5] Anne Meike Bokhorst. 2014. *Bronnen van legitimiteit: Over de zoektocht van de wetgever naar zeggenschap en gezag*. Ph.D. Dissertation. Tilburg University.
- [6] Roger Burkhardt, Nicolas Hohn, and Chris Wigley. 2019. Leading your organization to responsible AI. *McKinsey Analytics* (2019), 1–8.
- [7] Alexandra Chouldechova. 2017. Fair prediction with disparate impact: A study of bias in recidivism prediction instruments. *Big data* 5, 2 (2017), 153–163.
- [8] Eva Constantaras, Gabriel Geiger, Justin-Casimir Braun, Dhruv Mehrotra, and Htet Aung. 2023. Inside the suspicion machine. *WIRED* (2023). <https://www.wired.com/story/welfare-state-algorithms/>
- [9] Maaïke HT de Boer, Steven Vethman, Roos M Bakker, Ajaya Adhikari, Michiel Marcus, Joachim de Greeff, Jasper van der Waa, Emma M van Zoelen, Bart Kamphorst, et al. 2022. The FATE System Iterated: Fair, Transparent and Explainable Decision Making in a Juridical Case. In *CEUR Workshop*

- Proceedings*, Vol. 3121. CEUR-WS.
- [10] Upol Ehsan, Q Vera Liao, Michael Muller, Mark O Riedl, and Justin D Weisz. 2021. Expanding explainability: Towards social transparency in ai systems. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*. 1–19.
 - [11] Upol Ehsan and Mark Riedl. 2024. Explainable AI reloaded: Challenging the xai status quo in the era of large language models. In *Proceedings of the Halfway to the Future Symposium*. 1–8.
 - [12] Upol Ehsan, Elizabeth A Watkins, Philipp Wintersberger, Carina Manger, Nina Hubig, Saiph Savage, Justin D. Weisz, and Andreas Riener. 2025. New Frontiers of Human-centered Explainable AI (HCXAI): Participatory Civic AI, Benchmarking LLMs, XAI Hallucinations, and responsible AI Audits. In *5th ACM CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI*.
 - [13] Upol Ehsan, Philipp Wintersberger, Q Vera Liao, Elizabeth Anne Watkins, Carina Manger, Hal Daumé III, Andreas Riener, and Mark O Riedl. 2022. Human-Centered Explainable AI (HCXAI): beyond opening the black-box of AI. In *CHI conference on human factors in computing systems extended abstracts*. 1–7.
 - [14] Gabriel Geiger, Eva Constantaras, Justin-Casimir Braun, Htet Aung, and Evaline Schot et al. 2023. Suspicion Machines. *Lighthouse Reports* (2023). <https://www.lighthousereports.com/investigation/suspicion-machines/>
 - [15] Lisa Graichen, Matthias Graichen, and Mareike Petrosjan. 2022. How to Facilitate Mental Model Building and Mitigate Overtrust Using HCXAI. In *2nd ACM CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI*.
 - [16] David Gray Grant, Jeff Behrends, and John Basl. 2025. What we owe to decision-subjects: beyond transparency and explanation in automated decision-making. *Philosophical Studies* 182, 1 (2025), 55–85.
 - [17] Stephan Grimmelikhuijsen and Albert Meijer. 2022. Legitimacy of algorithmic decision-making: Six threats and the need for a calibrated institutional response. *Perspectives on Public Management and Governance* 5, 3 (2022), 232–242.
 - [18] Balint Gyevar, Nick Ferguson, and Burkhard Schafer. 2023. Bridging the Transparency Gap: What Can Explainable AI Learn From the AI Act? In *ECAI 2023*. IOS Press, 964–971.
 - [19] Sydney Howe, Anna Smak Gregoor, Carin Uyl-de Groot, Marlies Wakkee, Tamar Nijsten, and Rik Wehrens. 2024. Embedding artificial intelligence in healthcare: An ethnographic exploration of an AI-based mHealth app through the lens of legitimacy. *Digital Health* 10 (2024), 20552076241292390.
 - [20] Achim Hurrelmann, Steffen Schneider, and Jens Steffek. 2007. Introduction: Legitimacy in an age of global politics. In *Legitimacy in an age of global politics*. Springer, 1–16.
 - [21] Jinglu Jiang, Surinder Kahai, and Ming Yang. 2022. Who needs explanation and when? Juggling explainable AI and user epistemic uncertainty. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 165 (2022), 102839.
 - [22] Eugenia Kulakova, Nima Khalighinejad, and Patrick Haggard. 2017. I could have done otherwise: Availability of counterfactual comparisons informs the sense of agency. *Consciousness and cognition* 49 (2017), 237–244.
 - [23] Arto Laitinen and Otto Sahlgren. 2021. AI systems and respect for human autonomy. *Frontiers in artificial intelligence* 4 (2021), 151.
 - [24] Brian Y Lim, Anind K Dey, and Daniel Avrahami. 2009. Why and why not explanations improve the intelligibility of context-aware intelligent systems. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on human factors in computing systems*. 2119–2128.
 - [25] Henrietta Lyons, Eduardo Velloso, and Tim Miller. 2021. Conceptualising contestability: Perspectives on contesting algorithmic decisions. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction* 5, CSCW1 (2021), 1–25.
 - [26] Gennie Mansi and Mark Riedl. 2023. Why don't you do something about it? Outlining connections between AI explanations and user actions. In *3rd ACM CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI*.
 - [27] Vipin Pillai and Hamed Pirsiavash. 2021. Explainable models with consistent interpretations. In *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, Vol. 35. 2431–2439.
 - [28] Michael Ridley. 2024. Human-centered explainable artificial intelligence: An Annual Review of Information Science and Technology (ARIST) paper. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology* 76, 1 (2024), 98–120.
 - [29] Jon Rueda, Janet Delgado Rodríguez, Iris Parra Jounou, Joaquín Hortal-Carmona, Txetxu Ausin, and David Rodríguez-Arias. 2024. “Just” accuracy? Procedural fairness demands explainability in AI-based medical resource allocations. *AI & society* 39, 3 (2024), 1411–1422.
 - [30] Fritz Scharpf. 1999. *Governing in Europe: Effective and democratic?* Oxford University Press.
 - [31] Vivien Schmidt and Matthew Wood. 2019. Conceptualizing throughput legitimacy: Procedural mechanisms of accountability, transparency, inclusiveness and openness in EU governance. *Public Administration* 97, 4 (2019), 727–740.
 - [32] Jakob Schoeffer, Maria De-Arteaga, and Niklas Kuehl. 2022. On the relationship between explanations, fairness perceptions, and decisions. In *2nd ACM CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI*.
 - [33] Julian Senoner, Simon Schallmoser, Bernhard Kratzwald, Stefan Feuerriegel, and Torbjørn Netland. 2024. Explainable AI improves task performance in human-AI collaboration. *Scientific Reports* 14, 1 (2024), 31150.
 - [34] Dilruba Showkat, Shereen Bellamy, and Alexandra To. 2022. Fair and Trustworthy Welfare Systems: Rethinking Explainable AI in the Public Sector. In *2nd ACM CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI*, Vol. 2.
 - [35] Mark C Suchman. 1995. Managing legitimacy: Strategic and institutional approaches. *Academy of management review* 20, 3 (1995), 571–610.
 - [36] Isaac Taylor. 2024. Is explainable AI responsible AI? *AI & SOCIETY* (2024), 1–10.
 - [37] Jasper van der Waa, Tjeerd Schoonderwoerd, Jurriaan van Diggelen, and Mark Neerincx. 2020. Interpretable confidence measures for decision support systems. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies* 144 (2020), 102493.

- [38] Tom M van Engers and Dennis M de Vries. 2019. Governmental transparency in the era of artificial intelligence. In *Legal Knowledge and Information Systems*. IOS Press, 33–42.
- [39] Ruotong Wang, F Maxwell Harper, and Haiyi Zhu. 2020. Factors influencing perceived fairness in algorithmic decision-making: Algorithm outcomes, development procedures, and individual differences. In *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI conference on human factors in computing systems*. 1–14.
- [40] Mireia Yurrita, Agathe Balayn, and Ujwal Gadiraju. 2023. Generating Process-Centric Explanations to Enable Contestability in Algorithmic Decision-Making: Challenges and Opportunities. In *3rd ACM CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI*.
- [41] Alexandra ZYTEK, Sara Pidò, and Kalyan Veeramachaneni. 2024. LLMs for XAI: Future Directions for Explaining Explanations. In *4th ACM CHI Workshop on Human-Centered Explainable AI*.

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